

The new CAP after 2020 – The Brussels Colloquium of the CEDR of 25.10.2022 on the occasion of the 60th anniversary of the CAP and the 65th founding year of the CEDR^{.*}

Christian Busse

University of Bonn (Germany)

The Comité Européen de Droit Rural (CEDR) hosted a double anniversary on 25 October 2022 at the Brussels premises of the European Committee of the Regions (CoR). On the one hand, the 60th anniversary of the start of the CAP in 1962 and, on the other hand, the 65th anniversary of the foundation of the CEDR were celebrated. The CEDR was founded in 1957, the year in which the European Treaties were concluded and one year before the Stresa Conference, which marked the beginning of the conception of the CAP. CEDR is the umbrella organisation of the national agricultural law societies of Europe.

In order to enable German agricultural lawyers to participate in the CEDR, the Deutsche Vereinigung für Agrarrecht in Europa e.V. (DVARE) was founded in 1972 with the significant participation of members of the DGAR, which had been founded in 1964. The CEDR had initially been conceived only for cooperation between the agricultural law societies in the member states of the European Economic Community, while the DGAR advocated a pan-European association, in particular including Austria and Switzerland, and therefore stayed away from the CEDR. After the CEDR had opened up to all European countries, the DGAR joined the CEDR in 1974. As a result, the DVARE, which had in the meantime been renamed the Association for European and German Agricultural and Environmental Law (VAUR), merged with the DGAR in 1980. Since then, the DGAR alone has represented the agricultural lawyers in the CEDR, initially only West Germans until the fall of the Berlin Wall and then also the East Germans.¹

The highlight of CEDR's diverse activities is the European Agricultural Law Congress, which is usually held every two years and is hosted by a national agricultural law society, which means that it has already met in numerous European countries. The last one took place in September 2019 as the XXX. Congress in Poznań. There, in addition to the usual three agricultural law commissions, the form of the colloquium on the reform of the CAP, which was often used within the framework of the congress in the past, was revived², and the current colloquium was able to build on this. The XXXI Congress planned for 2021 in Cardiff had to be postponed to September 2023 due to the Corona pandemic.

* The contribution reflects the personal view of the author only. The author participated in the colloquium Deputy National Delegate of the DGAR to the CEDR. A German version of this article has been published in *Agrar- und Umweltrecht* 2022, p. 459-460.

¹ See Winkler, 30 Jahre Deutsche Gesellschaft für Agrarrecht 1964-1994, *Agrarrecht* 1995, p. 78 (79 f. and 85 f.).

² The conference proceedings are expected to be published in spring 2023.

The opening of the colloquium by CEDR President Geoff Whittaker was followed by a welcome address by MEP Ulrike Müller, who shared her experiences of the protracted negotiations of the current CAP reform, which will take effect on 1 January 2023. The first short presentation was given by MEP Herbert Dorfmann on the topic of "Background and Genesis". He described the most serious problem of decoupling as the fact that support has been linked to the mere ownership of agricultural land. Increased in particular by the financial crisis, the purchase of agricultural land as an investment has thus become considerably more lucrative. The Member States were very hesitant to counteract this negative development for the structure of agriculture, which is also shown by the current CAP again.

Furthermore, in view of the end of the baby boomer generation, Dorfmann stressed the need to make the agricultural sector an attractive profession for young people. As long as the average income is below that of many other professions and farmers are under increasing social pressure to justify themselves – for example from the food and environmental side – the opposite is the case. Dorfmann pointed out that farmers are traditionally not very willing to reform and, in view of the existing challenges, called for farmers to be more open-minded towards innovations.

Dorfmann also noted that in the recent past, the reference to food security as one of the CAP's objectives since 1958 had been ridiculed as backward-looking, but this had now changed fundamentally. The EU is a major exporter of food. However, if we take a closer look at individual product sectors, it becomes clear that there is in part a great dependence on imports – for example of soya for feeding purposes. In this respect, it is also a problem that more than four years have passed between the presentation of the legislative proposals by the European Commission in summer 2018 and the entry into force of the CAP reform on 1 January 2023. The framework conditions have changed dramatically since 2018, which is not sufficiently reflected in the CAP reform.

Cristina Carrasco, who represented Michael Niejahr on the topic "New Legislation and Implementation", outlined the genesis of the three CAP basic regulations from the perspective of the European Commission. She described the reasons for the long duration of the negotiations, which included 25 trilogues, 4 supertrilogues and hundreds of technical working meetings. A particular difficulty had been that this work had taken place almost exclusively online because of the Corona pandemic. The national CAP strategic plans – with the exception of Belgium, only one per Member State – had replaced 26 notifications in the area of direct payments as well as 65 sector strategies and 118 programmes in the area of rural development. Carrasco also described the European Commission's evaluation criteria and ARACHNE, a new tool against subsidy fraud.

On the part of the host, Isilda Gomes, who chairs the Commission for Natural Resources in the CoR, spoke on "Local and Regional Aspects". She emphasised the difficulty for the regions in the Member States to get involved in the CAP reform process. She assessed the legislative proposals of the European Commission as basically a step backwards with regard to the importance of the regions. However, in the course of the negotiations, it had been possible to include the regional aspect in eleven articles within the framework of the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation. The CoR will intensively pursue this aspect, which is of importance for the CoR, and will carry out an analysis of the regional aspects within the framework of the national CAP strategic plans.

Again from the perspective of the European Commission, Mihail Dumitru presented the process of submitting and approving the national CAP strategic plans, which has, at that time, not been fully completed, under the title "Instrument and National Implementation". By 25.5.2022, each Member

State had received an "observation letter" and thus comments on its submitted CAP strategic plan. In this context, Dumitru referred to some aspects – including a more intensive elaboration of the objectives and strengthening of the environmental and climate dimension – which had been strengthened in the context of the discussion on the submitted CAP strategic plans. So far, the European Commission has given final approval to nine CAP strategic plans. Dumitru also presented a preliminary overview of how the planned use of funds is distributed cumulatively in all Member States among five central areas of the CAP strategic plans – basic income support for sustainability: 52%; complementary redistributive income support for sustainability: 10%; coupled income support: 12%; complementary income support for young farmers: 2%; eco-schemes: 24%.

This was appropriately followed by Aneta Suchon from the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, who presented the current status of the implementation of the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation in Poland³ on the one hand and the corresponding status in Spain from a paper of Esther Muñiz Espada from the University of Valladolid. Among other things, Suchon explained the still ongoing process of national legislation in Poland and the resulting challenge of applying the most appropriate legal instruments in each case. In principle, all regulations in Poland would be decided at central government level and contractual forms would be the main instrument for implementation. At the same time, she announced an international online symposium at the University of Poznań on the national implementation of the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation for January 2023.

Finally, the Director General of DG AGRI, Wolfgang Burtscher, spoke about the "CAP in the Light of the European Environment and Climate Strategies" and showed, using the example of biodiversity, that the image spread by the European Court of Auditors, among others, does not always correspond to the facts. While concrete figures on the CAP's contribution to biodiversity are available, there are no figures on other economic sectors' respective contributions to achieving the EU's overall goal of increasing biodiversity. Often, the CAP would achieve positive environmental effects – for example in the promotion of mountain farming – without this being explicitly regulated as an objective of the respective measure. He called for the CAP not to make itself smaller than it is in pursuing the objectives of the Green Deal. He pointed to recitals 122 and 123 of the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation, according to which the Member States should take into account the objectives of the Green Deal when drawing up their national CAP strategic plans and the European Commission when assessing the CAP strategic plans submitted.

Finally, Burtscher referred to the fact that the focus of the general debate and thus the original CAP is moving away from primary agricultural production towards sustainable food systems. This raises the question of whether general food policy should be used to steer the agricultural economy. For example, interest groups are demanding a reduction of meat production by half, which could have immense effects on agriculture. In this respect, promotion and regulation policies are in conflict with each other.

In his closing remarks, Whittaker used the adage that whatever field is being worked in, there is always a higher level. He thanked all speakers, audience members and the host CoR and hoped for a future reunion in Cardiff. In this way, the colloquium, which was attended by a high calibre of speak-

³ The presentation of Prof. Dr Aneta Suchón is printed in *Agrar- und Umweltrecht* 2022, 460-462.

ers, came to an end. From the perspective of the European Parliament and the European Commission to the perspective of the Member States and the regional level, the many dimensions of the CAP were highlighted.